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HSV-1 infection of neural progenitor cells halts proliferation.

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We measured total transcription in NPC following infection with HSV-1 at specified multiplicity of infection to study transcriptional dynamics in cells of the human CNS following herpesvirus infection in physiologically relevant conditions. We describe here a cycling phenotype in neural progenitor cells resulting from herpes simplex infection. The proliferative phenotype was characterized by silencing of neural proliferation marker Pea15. We describe here an authentic proliferative defect associated with viral infection.

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